

FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF LUNCH PROGRAMME AND ITS INFLUENCE ON LEARNING OUTCOMES IN PUBLIC DAY SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN MOMBASA AND KILIFI COUNTIES, KENYA

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Abstract: The study was to assess financial management of lunch programme and their influence on learning outcomes in public day secondary schools in Mombasa and Kilifi Counties, Kenya. The research objective was to assess influence of financial management of lunch programme on learning outcomes public day secondary schools in Mombasa and Kilifi Counties, Kenya. The study population consisted of all Counties' 49 day secondary schools 940 teachers, 49 principals, 49 lunch coordinators and 18,847 students. Simple random sample and stratified random sampling were utilized in the research. The sample for each category of school was also drawn using simple random sampling. The sample size comprised 17 secondary schools, 17 principals, 17 lunch coordinators, 274 teachers and 377 students. This gave a total of six hundred and eighty five respondents from the two Counties. The study's major findings were that financial school lunch program management had a significant influence on realization of learning outcomes. The mixed research approach used in the study was primarily the descriptive survey design, in which quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously.

Keywords: Financial School Lunch Management, Learning Outcomes.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to UNESCO (2015), the school feeding program's goals are to improve children's concentration span by reducing periodic hunger, raise enrolment and attendance and reduce afternoon absenteeism (Aila, 2012). School lunch programs are largely utilized to improve learning results in schools (Mutua, 2014). The majority of the cash used to administer the school meal program come from the parents. Once money is secured, each school's Meal Programme Committee (SMPC) provides the necessary food based on meticulous planning. In 2008, Kenya established free day secondary education to allow all children to attend secondary school. However, there are education costs that the government does not account for in the FDSE. They include the cost of school meals, PTA fees and the cost of school uniform. Since households are forced to fund these expenditures, students' involvement has been hampered (Weru, 2014). School feeding programmes needs to be managed effectively if the desired results are to be obtained.

As indicated by National Food Service Management (Rainville & Carr, 2006), financial management is essential for school food service managers in America to prudently manage funds and maintain records. A few directors indicated that financial management is the most relevant of all skills for executives of new area school foodservice (Thomson et al., 2012). Budgetary administration influences the most crucial areas of the school foodservice program. The National Food Service Management Institute has developed budgetary management tools to assist school food service managers in securing money management skills and begin to track funds more effectively (Cater & Mann, 2005).

School feeding programs are costly since they include food. Governments are put under enormous strain by the costs of food management, logistics, and regulation, as well as the cost of food itself. When feeding is done within the schools, it becomes expensive because there is the additional cost of daily preparation of food and its delivery; however, this is a model that can enable community participation (Osiero, 2014). The most efficient programs are those that employ educational infrastructure for distribution and logistics. Programs that require costly equipment and supplies or building new infrastructure, can push up the cost of running them. Ways of minimizing the wastage occasioned by such things as spillage, leakage and black-market operations are needed to ensure program feasibility. Some SFP can be used to transfer income to families that are struggling and help attract young girls to enroll in school (Ross, 2010).

II. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The mixed method approach was adopted by the researcher. This method was advantageous since it allowed participants to test pertinent theories and provide detailed information (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003). Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. Detailed descriptions of educational occurrences are incorporated in descriptive survey designs. The study's target group included school administrators, teachers, lunch program coordinators, and students from public day secondary schools in Mombasa and Kilifi counties.

Simple random sampling and random stratified sampling were utilized in the study. Because it represented the target population and eliminated biased sampling, simple random sampling was utilized. Since stratified random sampling yielded more exact statistical results, it was used. Boys' Secondary Schools, Girls' Secondary Schools, and Mixed Secondary Schools were all sampled using stratified random sampling. The proportional technique was used to calculate the number of participating schools in each stratum.

Table 1: Sampling of Public Day Secondary Schools in Mombasa and Kilifi Counties.

Schools	Total Number of Schools	Numbers Selected	Percentage Selected (%)
Girls' Schools	12	5	42 %
Boys' Schools	14	5	36%
Mixed Schools	23	7	30%
Total	49	17	35 %

Questionnaires were used to gather data from principals, teachers, and students for the study. Questionnaires are a low-cost method of collecting data from large groups. According to Gay (2012), questionnaires are important because they allow respondents' views and ideas to be kept private. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2019), questionnaires were mostly used in descriptive research since they help gather information about present situations and are good for eliciting opinions. There were both open-ended and closed-ended questions on the questionnaires. To improve the validity of the tools, the investigator enlisted the help of his supervisors and sought expert advice.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The initial objective was to evaluate the financial management of the lunch program in the Kenyan counties of Mombasa and Kilifi, as well as its influence on learning outcomes in public day secondary schools. In order to attain this goal, the research sought to learn more about the financial management of the school feeding system

Financial Management of Lunch Programme – Principals and Teachers

Table 2 shows the information gathered from principals as well as the outcomes.

Table 2: The Financial Management of Lunch Programme - principals and Teachers (N=244)

Financial Areas	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Parents Funding	244	120	49.18	62	25.41	44	18.03	18	7.30
Budgeting by bursar	244	123	50.41	51	20.90	41	16.80	29	11.88
Cost of Schooling	244	103	42.21	77	31.56	43	17.62	21	8.61
Inability to pay (Poverty)	244	138	56.56	75	30.74	21	9.38	10	4.10
Programme Money	244	54	22.13	45	18.44	93	38.11	52	21.31
School Supplementing Programme	244	53	21.72	73	29.92	38	15.57	80	32.79

Source: Survey data, 2020

Key: 4= Strongly Agree 3= Agree 2. =Disagree 1. =Strongly Disagree

The majority of the 120 respondents (49.18 percent) answered that parents are the primary funder of the lunch program in table 4.8. More than half of the administrators and teachers 123 (50.41%) said the bursar is in charge of the lunch program finances. The majority of the respondents 103 (42.21 percent) said that paying for the lunch program increased the expense of education. More than half of the respondents 138 (56.56%) agreed that poverty caused parents to refuse to pay for the lunch program, while 10 (4.10%) disagreed. More than a third 93 (38.11 percent) disagreed that money for lunch programs is usually available.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviations of Financial Management of Lunch Programmes

Financial Management Areas	Total	mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error
Parents Funding	244	3.164	0.970	0.063
Budgeting by bursar	244	3.10	1.067	0.066
Cost of Schooling	244	3.074	0.968	0.063
Inability to pay (Poverty)	244	3.400	0.811	0.058
Programme Money	244	2.414	1.054	0.066
School Supplementing Programme	244	2.406	1.154	0.069

Source: Field Data (2020)

The means and standard deviations of the lunch program's financial management areas were also employed in the analysis. The parents' inability to pay for lunch programme due to poverty had a mean of 3.40, which is quite high, according to (Pimentel, 2019). Bursar's budgeting, parental funding, cost of attending school all had means above 3, which was significant. The lowest mean for schools that complemented the lunch program was 2.41, which is considered moderate by (Pimentel, 2019).

The overall mean for all the financial management components was 2.93, which was approximated to 3 is high. This implied that the respondents agreed that financial management of lunch programmes influences learning outcomes significantly. The overall standard deviation was 1.0, meaning that most respondents responded differently to questions that were otherwise similar. The sample mean is a true reflection of the population mean because the sample mean's overall standard error of the mean was only 0.06, which is extremely low.

Influence of Financial Management on Learning Outcomes of School Lunch Programme

The study also tried to find out from the principals and teachers how financial performance affected the Learning outcomes.

a) Influence of Financial Management on Learning Outcomes of School Lunch Programme- principals and Teachers

The results of principals and teachers are represented in the tables 4

Table 4: Influence of Financial Management on Learning Outcomes of School Lunch Programs by Principals and Teachers (N= 244)

Indicators of Learning Outcomes	Strongly agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly disagree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Improved performance	148	60.66	44	18.03	35	14.34	17	6.97
Improved discipline	132	54.10	57	23.36	36	14.75	19	7.79
Improved health status	113	46.31	74	30.32	17	6.97	40	16.39
Improved time management	184	75.41	17	6.97	17	6.97	26	10.66

Source: Field Data (2020)

According to table 4.10 more than half of the respondents 148 (60.66%) reported that well managed lunch programme lead to improved performance. Most of the principals and teachers 132 (54.10%) reported that there was improved discipline as a result of lunch programme. Majority of the respondents 113 (46.31%) stated that there was improved health status of students as result of lunch programme. Approximately three quarters of the respondents 184 (75.41%) indicated that there was improved time management as a result of lunch programme.

Financial Management Techniques of Lunch Programme on Learning Outcomes- Principal and Teachers

Figure 1 represents the findings of principals and teachers on financial management techniques of lunch programme on learning outcomes.

Financial Management Techniques of Lunch Programme, on Learning Outcomes- Principal and Teachers

Source: (2020)

Figure 1 demonstrates that 120 (50%) respondents indicated that parents primarily pay for the lunch program. The bursar is in control of the lunch program's finances, according to more than half of the 123 administrators and instructors (50.41%). One hundred and three respondents (42.21%) who made up the majority, claimed that paying for the lunch program raised the cost of school. One hundred and thirty eight (56.56%) of the respondents agreed that parents' refusal to pay for the lunch program was a result of their poverty, whereas 10(4.10%) respondents disagreed. 38.11 percent of respondents, or More than one third of respondents (38.11%) disagreed that funding for lunch programs is typically available. These findings agrees with those of one of the lunch coordinators in one of the school, who had this to say.

Most of the times when we have not paid for lunch programmes our children are sent home to go and bring the money. This is because the money we pay buy food for our children. When we get the money we pay through the bursar who issues us with receipt indicating payment of lunch programme.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were drawn based on the study's objective and findings:

In Mombasa and Kilifi Counties, the study aimed to determine the influence of the financial management of the lunch program on learning outcomes. According to the study's findings, the financial management of the lunch program greatly influenced student learning outcomes. Effective financial management of the school lunch program led in enhanced student health, active involvement in class, and better time management.

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